

COMPLIANT MULTIFUNCTIONAL WING STRUCTURES FOR HARVESTING SOLAR ENERGY

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Keywords: Miniature Air Vehicle, Compliant Wings, Flexible Solar Cells, Energy Harvesting, Multifunctional Performance

1 Introduction

Over the last several years, there has been an increasing interest in Miniature Air Vehicles, (MAVs). Due to their limitation in weight [1], MAVs rely on advanced lightweight structures and components to achieve flight. This requires the MAV to be powered by a small but efficient battery. A consistent problem that arises among different MAVs is the limitation to flight duration. Thus, new technologies for enabling energy to be harvested for long-term/distance missions are required. While technologies like flexible solar cells and piezofilms [2] exist to “harvest energy” during missions, they are difficult to integrate using their existing packaging because the added weight and stiffness decrease the load bearing capabilities and increase energy requirements.

To overcome these limitations, integration of energy harvesting elements (such as solar cells) into the critical structural components (such as wings) must be studied. This integration can be accomplished using transfer processes where the choice of substrate plays a more dominant role in the compliance of the structure. Compliant design issues can then focus on the thickness of the substrate, the elastic properties, the density, and the geometry and distribution of the energy harvesting element. The key to realizing a complete understanding of compliant design for these new “multifunctional structures” is a multi-stage multi-material molding process we have developed that enables us to completely integrate electronic components with polymer and polymer composite structural members. Thus, we are investigating experimental and computational multifunctional principles for guiding the design of compliant wing structures with integrated solar cells.

With an understanding of these principles, we propose a general model to quantify the benefits or drawbacks of design changes made to MAV wings. Making the time-in-flight a function of the consumption of energy due to thrust forces and accounting for the total power of the platform, one can predict how changes in wing design due to solar cell integration will affect the duration of flight time. This model was derived using University of Maryland’s Jumbo Bird, but the model can be extended to different types of MAVs, and allow researchers to explore new designs for multifunctional compliant energy harvesting structures subjected to aerodynamic forces.

2 Experimental Approach

2.1 Wing Design

The wings for this MAV are made up of Mylar foil or Mylar and supporting spars made of carbon fiber rods and tubes. The carbon fiber rods and tubes give the wing its structure while the Mylar makes up the body or skin of the wing. The initial design of the wings consisted of a flat wing design where the upstroke and downstroke of the MAV cancels out the generated forces and produced zero static lift. With these wings, the MAV relies solely on aerodynamic lift generated while the MAV is moving forward to keep it aloft. However, integrating solar cells to these wings adds more mass to the system and do not allow the MAV to stay aloft. Therefore, a new wing structure with a compliant front spar has been specifically designed for the integration of solar cells. These wings are designed to form a rounded pocket in the upstroke and straighten out on the downstroke. Compared to the previous set of wings, these wings generate a positive static lift. The rounded compliant spar provides a beneficial aerodynamic shape that allows the wing to experience less air resistance

during the upstroke. Even though these wings provide more static lift than the previous wings, the installation of solar cells still decreases the performance of these wings. The ability for the wings to deform to the rounded aerodynamic shape is restricted by the installation of solar cells. Through the integration of solar cells, the wing becomes more rigid since the solar cells are stiffer than the Mylar. Ergo, the attached solar cells should decrease the lift generated by these wings.

The compliant spar was designed for ideal durability, size, and weight. The spar is composed of two, 1/8" carbon fiber rods adjoined by a monolithic compliant section. All carbon fiber spars are manufactured by Midwest Products Co. Inc, and all under stock number 5720. A laser cutter is used to manufacture the compliant section from a 1/8" thick Delrin® sheet. Delrin® material was selected for its superior tensile strength, stiffness, creep resistance, and fatigue [3]. Another advantage of selecting Delrin® material is that it is easy to manufacture on the laser cutter. The inside carbon fiber rod is 5" long, the compliant section is 6" long, and the outside compliant spar is 7" long. The total horizontal length of the fully assembled compliant spar is 18". The compliant section of the spar weighs 9.2g. To maintain the shape of the wings, auxiliary spars extend down perpendicularly from the compliant spar at the top of the wing. This ensures that the entire wing maintains the shape necessary to generate the forces necessary for flight.

The integration of the solar cells also has an impact on overall wing performance. Three MPT6-75 Powerfilm® Solar cells were integrated to the wing. Each solar cell was 2.87 inches wide, 4.49 inches long, and weighed 2.3 grams. They have an operating voltage of 6 volts and produce a current of 50 mA in sunlight. Connecting these solar cells together, 150 mA of current can be generated. The solar cells are connected widthwise by adhering a small strip of Mylar between each cell. These solar cells are then adhered to the actual wing of the MAV. A rectangular section where the solar cells are to be integrated was first cut out of the wing. The solar cells were placed as close to the compliant spar and body of the MAV as possible. This is where the solar cells would have the smallest effect on the shapes the wing needs to take during flight. The solar cells were adhered

to the wing completing the construction of the wing. The completed wing can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Completed Compliant Multifunctional Wing for Harvesting Solar Energy

2.2 Wing Characterization

To quantify the effects that changes on the wings make on the overall performance of the MAV, a testing platform was developed. The platform is placed at the end of a wind tunnel and holds the MAV parallel to the ground. A frame was made out of Delrin® that holds the bird stationary at the top of the platform. Right underneath the frame, a 6 degree of freedom load cell combines the frame with the platform. The forces generated by MAV are translated onto the load cell. Using NI Signal Express, the signals/voltages from the load cell are recorded. The data is processed using Microsoft Excel and forces generated by the MAV are found. Figure 2 highlights how the load cell measures the forces generated by the wing.

Figure 2: Test Set-up used for Wing Characterization

Three sets of data were collected using the testing platform. First, the forces generated by the wing with rigid front spar. Then, a wing with compliant front spar was tested to determine the changes in wing performance with the new wing design. Finally, a wing with compliant front spar with solar cells was tested to

determine the effects solar cells have on wing performance.

To quantify the effectiveness of power generation, the voltage output from the solar cells was compared for wing with rigid front spar with solar cells and wing with compliant front spar with solar cells. For this test, we simply ran the MAV on the test stand outside on a sunny day with no clouds. To make sure we were consistent with our experiments, we put the test stand in the same position every time and tested within the same hour to make sure the position of the sun remained as consistent as possible. The wings with solar cells on the test stand can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3a: Wing with Rigid Front Spar on Test Stand. Figure 3b: Wing with Compliant Front Spar on Test Stand.

3 Experimental Results

3.1 Forces Generated by the MAV

The following Figures show the lift forces generated by the MAV with an incoming wind. Figures 4a and 4b show the results for a wing with rigid front spar with no solar cells attached.

The average aerodynamic lift produced by these wings was -7.98 grams. However, the maximum lift force generated by these wings was 315 grams. Figure 4b clearly shows how lift is being gained and lost throughout the flapping process. Whatever lift is gained during downstroke of the wings is quickly lost during the upstroke. These wings rely solely on the fact that the bird takes an angle of attack of 20° to produce aerodynamic lift through the thrust force generated by

the wings. Figures 4a and 4b show the results for a wing with compliant front spar with no solar cells.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4a: Time Dependent Lift Response of Wing with Rigid Front Spar. Figure 4b: Position Dependent Lift Response of Wing with Rigid Front Spar

The average lift for the wing with compliant front spar without solar cells was 49.7 grams. Thus, they generate static lift. In Figures 4a and 5b, the forces generated during the downstroke are not cancelled out by the upstroke as much. The ability for the wing with compliant front spar to deform during the upstroke decreases the opposing force generated by the wing. Figures 6a and 6b show the results for a wing with compliant front spar with solar cells.

(a)

(b)

(a)

(b)

Figure 5a: Time Dependent Lift Response of Wing with Compliant Front Spar without Solar Cells. Figure 5b: Position Dependent Lift Response of Wing with Compliant Front Spar without Solar Cells

The average lift for the wing with compliant front spar with solar cells is 34.5 grams. As expected, the Wing with compliant front spar with solar cells did generate a static lift with a smaller magnitude than the wing with compliant front spar without solar cells. The addition of solar cells caused a loss of 30% (15.2 grams) in lift force generation when compared to the wing with compliant front spar without solar cells. However, the lift force of the wing with compliant front spar with solar cells is still 42.5 grams higher than the wing with rigid front spar without solar cells.

Figure 6a: Time Dependent Lift Response of Wing with Compliant Front Spar with Solar Cells. Figure 6b: Position Dependent Lift Response of Wing with Compliant Front Spar with Solar Cells

The output in voltage for the wing with compliant front spar with solar cells was compared to the output in voltage for a wing with rigid front spar with solar cells. The results can be seen in Figures 7a and 7b.

(a)

Figure 7a: Output Voltage from Wing with Rigid Front Spar with Solar Cells. Figure 7b: Output Voltage from Wing with Compliant Front Spar with Solar Cells.

The voltage seen across the wing with compliant front spar was much more consistent from start to finish. For the wing with rigid front spar, the solar cells move so much in and out of the sunlight that it takes some time for the solar cells to reach their operating voltage. On the other hand, since the wing with compliant front spar has a curved surface for the solar cells, the solar cells are consistently in sunlight and immediately reach the operating voltage for the solar cells.

4. Modeling of Multifunctional Performance

MAV performance, which can be quantified through time-in-flight, t_f , or payload capacity, is affected by three main components: the power supplied to the motor, and the thrust and lift forces generated by the flapping wings. Power, lift, and thrust are affected by: (1) the area of the wing, A ; (2) the distribution of the stiffness in the wing, ϕ , which is a function of both carbon fiber spar placement and the solar cell placement, since both affect the compliance; and (3) flapping frequency, f , in Hertz. These relationships, seen in equation 7, were the starting point for the development of the theoretical equation for the time-in-flight. Time-in-flight is a function of power supplied to the motor, P , lift, L , and thrust, T .

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P(A, \phi, f) \\
 &T(A, \phi, f) \\
 &L(A, \phi, f) \\
 &t_f = f(P, L, T)
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Time-in-flight can also be written as the energy stored in the platform, U_{stored} , divided by the average power expended by the platform over time, P_{expended} . The energy stored in the MAV platform equipped with solar cells is the sum of the energy stored in the batteries, U_{battery} , and the power provided by the solar cells, $P_{\text{solarcell}}$ for the time-in-flight. Equation (1) then becomes:

$$t_f = \frac{U_{\text{stored}}}{P_{\text{expended}}} = \frac{U_{\text{battery}} + P_{\text{solarcell}} t_f}{P_{\text{expended}}} \tag{2}$$

The expended average power is a function of the amount of work done by the motor. This work is affected by two coupled factors: the thrust produced by the wings and the velocity at which the MAV is flying. Assuming constant velocity, the only variable in power is the thrust. We previously determined that the thrust in these wings is proportional to the squared frequency value at which the wings are flapped, which are shown in Figure 8 [4].

Figure 8: Thrust vs. Frequency for compliant flapping wings [4].

Based on these findings, the average power expended by the platform, defined by equation (3), is equal to the thrust produced by the wings at the flapping frequency, T , multiplied by the flapping frequency, f , and a proportionality constant, k . The proportionality constant must be calculated for each different wing set using equation (4), as it changes based on the flapping frequency and the corresponding thrust value. The resulting time-in-flight equation is described by equation (5).

$$P = kTf \tag{3}$$

$$k = TfP_0 \tag{4}$$

$$t_f = \frac{U_{battery} + P_{solarcell}t_f}{kTf} \quad (5)$$

where $P_0=45W$ corresponds to the power of the brushless motor used for our MAV.

Rearranging equation (5) results in the following:

$$t_f kTf - P_{solarcell}t_f = U_{battery} \quad (6)$$

In order to further reduce the equation, a few assumptions must be made. While thrust is not necessarily a constant value throughout a specified flight time, it is assumed constant based on the way the value was experimentally measured. The energy stored in the battery is based on its overall capacity and the average voltage across the pack. The power provided by the solar cells is based on the area of the wing the solar cell covers, while the thrust is based on the area of the wing, its stiffness distribution, ϕ , and the flapping frequency, f . After rearranging equation (6) to solve for t_f , the final equation for the time-in-flight becomes:

$$t_f = \frac{U_{battery}}{kTf - P_{solarcell}} \quad (7)$$

5 Time-in-flight Predictions

Predictions for time-in-flight can be generated using equation (7). Based on this equation, six quantities must be known in order to solve for time-in-flight: the energy stored in the batteries, the thrust characteristics based on the solar cell area and the cell distribution, the flapping frequency of the MAV, the power generated by the solar cell based on the area covered, and the proportionality constant, k . The thrust values were measured for two wing designs with different spar configurations, designated as Wing A and B, at the maximum flapping frequency of 6.1 Hz, both with the different solar cell configurations and without the solar cells.

The power ratings for the solar cells were listed in Table 1. The energy stored in the battery pack, the largest of which contained three 300mAh batteries wired in series, was calculated by multiplying the capacity (0.3Ah) by the voltage, which was 11.1V (three 3.7V batteries wired in series). The energy stored in the battery pack was therefore 12 kJ. Finally, the flapping frequency for the

original wing sets at the thrust values comparable to the values produced by the solar cell wings had to be determined, so the time-in-flight values can be compared. The power consumed by the motor is proportional to the thrust at a certain flapping frequency multiplied by that flapping frequency, thus the flapping frequency at the average maximum thrust value produced by the solar cells on each wing type must be calculated. Because thrust is a function of the value of flapping frequency squared, the flapping frequency can be determined by comparing the second order polynomial variations of the original wing thrust and the thrust produced by the wing with solar cells. The frequency that occurs at the intersection of the average maximum thrust value for the solar cells and the original data best-fit line was the flapping frequency. Figure 9 shows the plots of thrust versus flapping frequency for the Wing A and wing B spar configurations, respectively.

Table 1: Solar Cell Data

Solar Cell	Area (in ²)	Power Rating (W)	mA Rating (mA)
2x5	3.90	0.07	25
3x5	5.25	0.06	22
3x7	4.95	0.09	22
7x3	8.97	0.18	50

(a)

(b)

Figure 9: Thrust versus flapping frequency for (a) Wing A and (b) Wing B

From previous two figures, the flapping frequency for each of the wing configurations was determined by obtaining the flapping frequency at the intersection of the original curve with the dashed line indicating the average thrust value for the wing with solar cells. The flapping frequency required to generate 24.6 grams force of thrust for wing A was 5.1 Hz, while the flapping frequency required to generate 33.5 grams force for wing B was 6.0 Hz. Using these values of frequency in the equation, time-in-flight was calculated for the original wing sets as well as the wing sets with solar cells. Table 2 compares data for the thrust, flapping frequency, and calculated time-in-flight for the two original wing configurations. Table 3 compares the thrust, flapping frequency, and calculated time-in-flight for the wing B solar cell configurations with the original wing B performance. Table 4 compares the thrust, flapping frequency, and calculated time-in-flight for the wing A solar cell configurations with the original wing A performance.

Table 2: Data for six wing configurations

Wing Design	Thrust (g)	Frequency (Hz)
A	34.9	6.1
B	35.8	6.1

Since the power supplied to the motor is the same for each wing, the proportionality constant for each wing set was a different value to obtain that 45 W of power supplied. Thus, the maximum time-in-flight is 13.3

minutes for the motor and battery pack that is used. The lack of variation in time-in-flight between the wing-sets was present because other effects, including power loss and lift, are not considered. Also, the significant loss in thrust between the different wing designs was not accounted for in the proportionality constant calculation, so it was not a factor in the overall time-in-flight.

Table 3: Δt_f for wing A solar cell configurations

Wing Design	Thrust (g)	Frequency (Hz)	Time-in-flight reduction (min)
2x5	23.4	6.1	9.4
3x5	25.0	6.1	10.3
3x7	26.5	6.1	11.0
7x3	23.5	6.1	9.4
Original A	24.6	5.1	0

The time-in-flight values presented in Table 3 show that while there was little variation between the different solar cell configurations, the time-in-flight for the solar cell configurations was reduced by 40% when compared with the original wing construction flapping with the same thrust value. This significant difference occurred because the solar cell output, which was only about 1% of the consumption rate, does not recharge the battery fast enough to impact time-in-flight. However, the difference in thrust was large enough that it greatly reduced the time-in-flight for the solar cells, since the thrust was much less for those configurations.

Table 4: Δt_f for wing B solar cell configurations

Wing Design	Thrust (g)	Frequency (Hz)	Time-in-flight reduction (min)
2x5	32.4	6.1	0.3
3x5	32.0	6.1	0.2

3x7	33.7	6.1	0.9
7x3	35.9	6.1	1.7
Original B	33.5	6.0	0

The time-in-flight values for Table 4 show that there was again very little difference between the four solar cell configurations; however, when compared with the original wing configuration, there was only a 5% loss in time-in-flight for a wing producing a similar thrust value. Like the wing A configurations, the solar cell output was only 1% of the power consumption rate of the motor. Unlike the wing A configurations, however, the solar cell configurations for wing B produces thrust values that were only slightly smaller than the original wing design; thus, the time-in-flight values were only slightly smaller.

Table 5 compares the results for time-in-flight between the solar cell configurations with the original values for wings A and B accounting for the energy harvesting ability and the power consumption due to the thrust forces in Tables 3 and 4. From this comparison, it can be seen that the solar cell configurations for both sets of wings produced similar time-in-flight values. While the original wing A design produced a significantly higher time-in-flight value than its solar cell configurations, the original wing B design produced only a slightly higher value than its solar cell configurations. This indicates that it may be preferable to implement solar cells should with the wing B design, as the change in thrust was not as detrimental to flight time.

Table 5: Comparison solar cell effects on t_f for wings A and B

Wing Design	A (min)	B (min)
Original	7.8	4.7
2x5	4.7	4.6
3x5	4.4	4.7
3x7	4.1	4.4

7x3	4.7	4.2
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6 Conclusions

To combat limitations in flight duration for MAVs, new technologies in energy harvesting have been integrated to existing structures of the MAV. More specifically, flexible solar cells were integrated to the wings of an MAV. The existing wing structure had to be redesigned to achieve more static lift during the flapping cycle. This led to the development of a wing with compliant front spar that generates more lift during the downstroke of the flapping cycle than the upstroke of the flapping cycle. These wings generated an increase of 49.7 grams of static lift. As expected, the addition of solar cells reduced the lift generated by the new wing with compliant front spar. The wing with compliant front spar with integrated solar cells produced 34.5 grams of lift; however, this is still 42.5 grams more lift than the wing with rigid front spar produced. These wings still produced more lift, and the energy harvesting capabilities of these wings is a drastic improvement in terms of overall performance of the MAV. The wing with compliant front spar with solar cells also harvested energy more efficiently than the wing with rigid front spar with solar cells. A new model for time-in-flight predictions was derived from the power of the overall system and forces generated by the MAV. Using two different wing designs and four different solar cells, the time-in-flight was predicted for each combination of wing and solar cell using data collected.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by Dr. Byung-Lip “Les” Lee at AFOSR through grant FA95501210158.

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